
Physical Carrying Capacity and Tourism Development of “KAAS PATHAR”

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Abstract:

Tourism plays a vital role in changing and developing tourist places. For Sustainable Ecotourism, the concept of carrying capacity in tourism needs to be applied. This concept of carrying capacity gives a inclusive importance in the development of tourism in physical, social or economic aspects. This concept is applied, in a tourist destination by the stake holders in tourism, namely tourists, locals and tour operators may be great advantages of tourist center for Sustainable development. The main objective of present research paper is to analyze the physical carrying capacity of “Kaas pathar” for the Sustainable development.

Keywords: *Carrying capacity, Sustainable tourism, Sustainable development, Ecotourism.*

Introduction:

Tourism sector plays an important role in economic development of countries as well as local area. Tourism help for conservation of Natural, archaeological and historic sites and prevent decline or vanishing of these sites. The tourism sector also has significant backward linkages and creates multiple effects which extend to manufacturing sector in the form of demand for souvenirs, handicrafts and mementos, as also to the agriculture sector which supplies food products for tourists.

Now days for the Sustainable tourism Carrying capacity concept applied tourism industry. Carrying capacity is widely applied in tourism and recreation studies since the 1960s, although some authors trace its emergence to as far back as 1930. while it can be viewed as an important concept in the ultimate emergence of sustainable tourism conversation,

Measurements of carrying capacity were first used as a way of deciding optimum stocking rates in agriculture. measurements of carrying capacity have been utilised in fields such as ecology, biology and population studies. In livestock studies, carrying capacity was defined as the maximum number of grazing animals that could make use of a defined area and this natural-resource based tradition of carrying capacity has informed many studies in tourism.

Tourism industry emerged in the academy and policy communities. Sustainable tourism, which actively seeks to draw links between the local and the global measurements of carrying capacity concentrate on local factors when evaluating the limits to tourism development.

The United World Tourism Organization defines carrying capacity as ‘the maximum number of people that may

visit a tourist purpose at the same time, with out causing damage of the physical, economic, socio-cultural environment and an unacceptable decrease in the quality if visitors' satisfaction'.

There is one simple measure of carrying capacity that can be evenly and equally applied to all destinations and attractions because they are not homogeneous in their morphology and structure. In fact, it is most commonly split into at least four elements, and sometimes more. *Getz* splits carrying capacity into six categories, physical, economic, perceptual, social, ecological and political.

- Physical carrying capacity of a tourist resource is the maximum use of the resource that can take place by tourists, before the resource begins to be unacceptably degraded.
- Economic carrying capacity of a tourist resource is the maximum use of the resource that can take place by tourists before leading to an unacceptable level of economic dependency on tourism in the area of the resource.
- Perceptual carrying capacity is a measurement of tourist's perceived level of carrying capacity in a tourist resource, beyond which tourists perceive there source as over-crowded.
- Social carrying capacity refers to the maximum use of a tourist resource that can take place, without causing unacceptable levels of local negative feeling towards tourism.
- The ecological carrying capacity of a tourist resource is the maximum use level that can take place without causing unacceptable damage to the natural environment of the resource.
- Political carrying capacity refers to the maximum use that can take place of a tourist resource without causing political instability, for

example,conflicts overland-rights or control of the incomes from tourism.

The implementation of measures of carrying capacity in the management of a tourism destination can involve visitor management techniques such as improving signage and managing tourism flows on a site, as well as using reservation and booking systems. It can also be implemented at more strategic levels through policy and regulations that relate to tourism development. In this study calculating physical carrying capacity of kaas pathar.

Objectives:

1. To analyze the geographical setup of study region.
2. To analyze the physical carrying capacity of study region.
3. To analyze the economical growth of study region.

Significance of Research Work:

Present research work focus on the Sustainable ecotourism development of kaas plateau. This work useful for managing the tourism sector for growth of tourist center kaas pathar. This work helpful to analysis of positive effect on study region.

Study Region:

Kaas Plateau is also known as the local name *kaas pathar*. The study region Geographically located at 17°43' - 17°45'N and 73°47' - 73°56'E, in the Satara district of Maharashtra, it is situated at an altitude of 1200 metres and is 10 sq. km in area. Located in the Satara district of Maharashtra .Kaas Plateau (or *Kaas Pathar*, as it's locally known) is part of Western Ghats, hotspot for Biodiversity Heritage. In 2012, World Heritage Committee meeting in Saint Petersburg in Russia inscribed the Kaas Plateau as UNESCO World Natural Heritage Site

among 39 other serial sites. The plateau, where the grasslands lie on the volcanic soil layer of few centimeters which turns into a

'plateau of flowers' during monsoon season, particularly from *August to early October*.

STUDY REGION - Kaas Plateau

Geographical setup of Study Region:

The region of Western Ghats in India was inscribed as the 39 serial WNHSS by the UNESCO in July 2012. These 39 sites of Western Ghats are spread over the area of 7953.15 km² and four Indian states. As part of the Sahyadri range of mountains' northern sub-cluster, the state of Maharashtra inhabits Koyna Wildlife Sanctuary, Chandoli National Park, Radhanagari Wildlife Sanctuary and Kaas plateau all in circle of about 200 kms. The area of 1972.85 hectares of the "Kaas plateau" is inscribed as the WNHSS-World Natural Heritage Site for its unique, endemic ecosystem and for its outstanding universal values that included rich biodiversity. The plateau is situated at the height of approximately 1213 meters above sea level. The volume of rainfall during June to October, called as monsoon season, at Kaas is about 2500 to 3000 m.m. These weather conditions nurture more than 850 species of flora during the flowering season. The plateau is home for around 350 flowering plants that include species listed as rare, endemic and threatened by Botanical Survey of India and International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN). Along with these flowering plants, many species of medicinal values and some large

and small species that are new to science have been discovered at the plateau. The heritage site of Kaas is approximately 25 km away from Satara, the nearest town and district place. The plateau of Kaas inhabits rich natural heritage of highly specialized edaphic plant groups with about 350 flowering plant species and exceptional aesthetic beauty. The outstanding universal value of Kaas is its flowers and their naturally attractive aesthetics. Most of these ephemeral communities of rock-out crops are insect pollinated and they mass bloom to attract pollinators. They have a very short growing season.

Methodology and Data Collection:

The Present study work based on the secondary source data, secondary data obtain from district censuses, socio-economic abstract of satara district (2011), Annual publish Report, Research papers, and collected data are processed and represented by essential methods, physical carrying capacity technique use in this research work.

Methods of Carrying Capacity Assessment:

The greatest number of visitors that can really correlate with a certain space

within a specific time period is known as physical carrying capacity (PCC). The PCC may be calculated using the formula below:

$$PCC = \frac{S}{sp} \times NV$$

$$NV = \frac{HV}{tV}$$

HV = Open hours

tV = required time to walk every trial.

Where:

S = available area for public use.

sp = area required per user (m²)

RF – Rotation Factor (the number of allowable daily visits)

Carrying capacity estimation for kaas pleateau

Physical carrying capacity. $PCC = \frac{S}{sp} \times NV$

The available area for visitor use is 10.00 km²

Area required per user = 40 m²

Open period of the Protected Area = 9 hours.

Average time of one visit = 9 hours

Rotation factor : Open period / Average time of one visit

kaas pleateau remains open for whole day (9 hours) for day visitors, and average time of visit is 9 hrs. This means theoretically, a person could make 1 visits in one day.

Thus,

$$PCC = \frac{S}{sp} \times NV$$

$$(NV = \frac{HV}{tV})$$

HV = Open hours.

tV = required time to walk every trial.

$$1 \text{ km}^2 = 1000000 \text{ m}^2$$

$$= 10.00 \text{ km}^2 \times 1000000 \text{ m}^2 / 40 \text{ m}^2 \times 9/9$$

$$= 10000000 \text{ m}^2 / 40 \text{ m}^2 \times 1$$

$$= 2,50,000 \text{ tourist per day.}$$

Thus pcc of kaas pleateau is 2,50,000 tourist per day.

From the estimation it was found that physical carrying capacity of “Kaas pleateau” is 2,50,000 visitors can visit per day, which means In a calendar 2,50,000 x 70 = 1,75,00,000 tourists can visit kaas pleateau year In flowering period August to early October .

Tourism Development of Kaas Pleateau:

The area of 10.00 km² of the “Kaas plateau” is inscribed as the WNHS-World Natural Heritage Site for its unique, endemic ecosystem and for its outstanding universal values that included rich biodiversity. In 2012, Kaas Plateau emerged as a National Heritage. From that it can be seen that there has been a drastic change in the tourism business of Kaas Plateau. Every year the number of tourists visiting Kaas Plateau is increasing and the revenue of Kaas Plateau is also increasing. As a result, the tourism industry has been greatly boosted and employment opportunities have been provided to the surrounding rural areas. The plans show that the government aims to take the Kaas Plateau towards sustainable development through various schemes. This will increase the per capita income of the local people and lead to the development of the region and preserve this resource for future generations. Statistics till date show an increase in the number of tourists visiting the Kaas Plateau every year as well as an increase in revenue.

Financial Statement of Kaas Plateau:

Kaas Plateau is gaining popularity among tourists as a hub for eco-tourism. Every year the number of tourists visiting Kaas Plateau is increasing. Therefore, Kaas Plateau is trying to become an economic development engine of eco-tourism center. In 2012 world heritage committee meeting inscribed cast plateau as a UNESCO World National Heritage site.

Since 2012, Kaas Plateau has started to be known as a tourism area in the country and abroad. In 2012, 91 thousand 167 tourists visited Kaas Plateau and the revenue of Kaas Plateau was 11 lakh 72 thousand 564. The number of tourists visiting in 2013 has increased over the previous year and the revenue of the previous year has also increased. In 2013,

128414 tourists visited and collected a revenue of 18 lakh 53 thousand 10. In 2014, the number of tourists decreased slightly from the previous year and the revenue was 14 lakh 36 thousand 960. Revenue generated by 99280 tourist visited to the kaas plateau. 2015 total number of visitor is 125923 and revenue generated 13 lakh 16 thousand 730.

The highest amount of revenue was generated in 2016 the total amount of INR

1,17, 81,130 was generated as a result of 5 to 10% in increase in the parking and entry fees.

Reflection of this decision on the tourist arrival seen in 2017 less in number cause of increasing the parking and entry fees. In 2017 total 88,456 tourist visited INR 9700000 Revenue generated. 2018, 2019, Tourist visited to kaas pathar that was 90,482, 85,046 respectively. Revenue was 1,05,53,779 in 2018, 1,00,82,240 in 2019.

Number of Visitors and Annual Revenue

Sr. No	Year	No. of tourist visited	Revenue
1	2012	91167	11,72,564
2	2013	128414	18,53,010
3	2014	99280	14,36,960
4	2015	125923	13,16,730
5	2016	73,523	1,17,00,456
6	2017	88,456	97,00,000
7	2018	90482	1,05,53,779
8	2019	85046	1,00,82,240

(Source- TERRE year book 2012- 2017)

The ticketing system for visiting the plateau has witnessed a few reforms over the last five years, which reflected into the number of visitors and revenue generation. Unlike 2016, the system of multiple tickets for various activities such as fees for camera, guide, parking, local commute etc. was

brought under single entry ticket of 100 INR in 2017. This helped in avoiding discrepancies in accounting records and generated equal revenue as compared to last year.

Revenue Utilization:

The revenue generated from the Kaas Plateau tourism business is utilized for the development of the tourism hub. These funds are used for the development

of surrounding rural settlements. Kusumbi Mura, Ekiv, Kaasani, Pategnar are the villages beneficiary villages in kaas plateau tourist centre.

Revenue Utilization

Infrastructure and Maintenance

Conservation Activities

Community Employment During the Flowering Season

Development in Member Villages (Yet To Be Distributed)

In 2017, approximately 60% (approximately 50,00,000 INR) of the total revenue (approximately 97,00,000 INR) was spent on infrastructure development, conservation purposes and employment in

the community. The remaining amount of funds is going to be distributed amongst the member villages for development initiatives

Revenue Generation during the Year 2019:

	No. of Visitors	Revenue INR
Online Registration	33,838	33,83,800
Offline Registration	51,208	51,20,500
Students	3,566	71,320
Senior Citizens	8,946	-
Fines Collected	2	1,500
Sale from Tea	-	41,700
Guide Fee	-	59,000
Parisar Darshan	-	54,400
Offseason Tourist	5,295	1,05,900
Bus Fee	-	12,44,120
Total Revenue	-	10,082,240

(Source- TERRE year book 2019-20)

(T.E.R.R.E – Technology, Education, Research & Rehabilitation for The Environment)

Conclusion:

The research presented a practical attempt at measuring kaas tourist potential in order to achieve this objective. With the use of calculations physical and real carrying capacity of kaas was estimated. The physical carry capacity of the study was high in study region of kaas plateau.

In the present research paper the physical karean capacity of Kaas Plateau has been calculated and it is seen to play an important role in the potential development of Kaas Plateau. In the future, the number of tourists visiting Kaas Plateau will see a huge increase. For sustainable development of resources, as well as for economic advancement, the concept of sustainable development should be applied by

searching for potential resources and using them properly, planning is necessary for continuous and sustainable development of resources of Kaas Plateau.

Kaas Plateau has great potential for growth of tourism business. Kaas Plateau became a major tourism revenue generating center in Maharashtra in the form of tourism center in future. This will enable socio-economic development of surrounding rural settlements.

Suggestion:

1. Online advertising method should be adopted about Kaas tourist destination.
2. All the convenient services should be provided to all the tourists like local, country, foreign.
3. Sustainable development should be planned for the Kaas Plateau with a view to developing it as an environmental tourism destination.
4. Surrounding Environmental sites of Kaas Plateau should be identified and included in Kaas Plateau.

5. Local community should be made more aware about the linkages between conservation activities, their sustainable living and the need for practical financial management.

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